

Math Software in Online Engineering Education

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Abstract

The article describes a teaching model with the support of mathematical software, which can be effectively used in online education and face-to-face teaching. The model was developed as part of the project solution with the support of the KEGA agency entitled Online Teaching Model with an emphasis on increasing the quality of engineering education during a possible pandemic and a project of the KEGA agency entitled Interactive Teaching Materials from Statistics and Design of Experiments. Based on the analysis results, we identified interactive Internet applications suitable for use in individual content parts of mathematics. Pedagogical experiments must be evaluated to verify didactic effectiveness, but interim results suggest that math software has its merits in teaching mathematics.

Keywords

engineering education, math software, mathematics, online education

1 Introduction

Teaching mathematics is often tricky because many are afraid of it. Fear of mathematics is already formed in primary school (Lazaros, 2013) and can significantly affect academic results. (Leppävirta, 2011) Therefore, it is essential to determine the causes of this fear and look for a way to minimise it. As one of the ways to overcome the fear of mathematics, Leppävirta (2011) suggests increasing the emphasis on conceptual understanding of mathematics, increasing the diversity of student assessment and supporting the individualisation of learning styles and strategies. We consider ICT to be a suitable tool for individualising studies. Mathematics teachers complement the traditional teaching model with strategies that emphasise conceptual understanding, active learning, and relevant applications (e.g. (Orszaghova, 2018; Phuong et al., 2022; Rahman et al., 2012)) The quality of mathematics teaching largely determines the competence of future engineers. (Firouzian et al., 2012; Noskov & Shershneva, 2005; Schaathun, 2022) The goal of teaching mathematics at a technical university should, therefore, be the teaching of mathematical foundations following the requirements of the curriculum, cultivating a mathematical “feeling” and developing skills in mathematical modelling of the problems of the studied profession. (Orszaghova & Greganova, 2017) An essential feature of engineers when creating mathematical models is their ability to solve non-standard problems. Thus, the inability to solve them is the reason for the difficulties of university students in studying mathematics for engineers. This fact is also supported by the findings of Firouzian et al. (2012), who state in their study that engineering students in anonymous questionnaires recommended more extensive use of software for solving

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mathematical problems to improve mathematics teaching, increasing practical exercises and solving practical problems on tasks from application disciplines for an easier understanding of mathematical concepts. These findings only further confirm, by our experience, the importance of a holistic approach to creating a mathematics curriculum in an engineering study with full use of the potential of mutual enrichment of teaching both professional subjects and mathematics. Moreover, this approach is facilitated by the use of ICT. The article describes a teaching model with the support of mathematical software, which can be effectively used in online and face-to-face education.

2 Methodology

The teaching model, with the support of mathematical software, was developed as part of the project solution. The goal was that mathematics should not only serve as a “sieve” but that students should not perceive it as a necessary evil to overcome if they want to study programs that interest them. On the contrary, by applying the teaching model, we want to make teaching the introductory mathematics course more attractive for students. We want to make the teaching more illustrative and, therefore, more effective. So that even students who do not have mathematical talent can continue their preparation for the engineering profession.

Tab. 1: Analysis results of open-source mathematical software

The name of the software	Atribút	Control complexity	Reliability of calculations or display	Availability of support
WinPlot	graphic	3	5	3
Desmos	graphic	5	4	5
Geogebra 3D	graphic	5	5	5
WolframAlpha	computational and graphic	4	4	4
wxMaxima	computational	3	4	3
Matrix calculator	computational	5	5	4

Source: authors

Using software in teaching mathematics can also help achieve the stated goal. Based on the analysis results, we identified interactive Internet applications suitable for use in individual content parts of mathematics. We established four analysis criteria: content, difficulty of control, consistency of calculations, and availability of user support. We analysed the selected mathematical software in terms of content and determined the type of software. If the software only allows us to perform calculations, we assign it a type - computational. If it only allows display, the assigned type is - graphic. If the software allows us to perform calculations and is also suitable for effective representation, we have assigned its type - computational and graphic. We evaluated the control complexity on a scale from one to five. We assigned a value of five if the control is simple, intuitive and user-friendly, and we set a value of one if the control of

the software is more complex and not very user-friendly. For example, it is necessary to remember the syntax. For use in teaching mathematics, we have selected software with a value of at least three.

The other analysis criterion was software reliability, i.e., consistency of calculations or the accuracy of graphic displays. We assigned a value of five to reliable software. When we find n inconsistencies in calculations or display inaccuracies, we reduce the value by n points. We also used the five-level scale in the evaluation from the point of view of the availability of user support. On a five-point scale, we assigned a value of five if user support is readily available, i.e. the user can easily find help with problems, e.g. syntax. Otherwise, we assigned a value of one. I.e., if user support is not readily available, the user must search longer. Table 1 shows the results of the analysis of open-source mathematical software.

Subsequently, after choosing suitable mathematical software, we proposed the use of the software in the content parts of the introductory mathematics course for students of the technical university. (Table 2) We assigned values to the software:

- “Yes” if it is suitable for use in the given content section,
- “Possibly” if use is possible in some part of the solution,
- “No” if using the software in the given content section is inappropriate.
- Three stages were necessary to implement the model.
- 1st stage. Creation of methodical materials. They were designed to make it easier for students to work with the software and to inspire them to use it effectively. The materials contain inspiring examples of using mathematical applications to solve problems.
- 2nd stage. Alerting students to pitfalls in calculations, as well as inaccuracies when displaying graphs of functions. Critical acceptance of the outputs is essential when using open-source mathematical software. The results obtained do not always agree with the mathematical theory; that is, they are not correct from a professional point of view. For example, WolframAlpha will list the multiple roots of an algebraic equation only once. The student must know that an algebraic equation of the n th degree has n roots, and some are multiple. For the above reasons, the student should not passively receive what is presented. Through critical thinking, a constructivist approach, and gaining experience, the student should gradually build an estimate of the given mathematical situation.
- 3rd stage. Use of software in the phase of solving tasks and in the phase of checking the correctness of the solution. In the task-solving phase, it is recommended that students use the software for routine mathematical operations necessary to solve a mathematical problem. For example, if it is necessary to create an analytical expression of a particular plane given by three points, an efficient solution is to calculate the coordinates of the normal vector of the plane. The fastest way is to determine the vector product of two vectors lying in the plane. That is, it is necessary to calculate the determinant of the 3rd-degree matrix. In this part, it is advisable to use mathematical software. (wxMaxima, Matrix calculator)

Tab. 2: Proposal for the use of software in the content parts of the introductory mathematics course

	WinPlot	wxMaxima	Desmos	Geogebra 3D	Wolfram Alpha	Matrix calculator
Algebraic equations	no	yes	possibly	possibly	yes	no
Matrices, Systems Determinants	no	yes	possibly	possibly	yes	yes
Vectors in E3	no	no	no	yes	yes	yes
Coordinate systems	yes	no	yes	yes	yes	no
Linear shapes in E3	yes	no	no	yes	yes	no
Properties of functions	yes	no	yes	yes	yes	no
Sequences and limits	no	yes	no	no	yes	no
Functions and limits	no	yes	no	possibly	yes	no
Rules for differentiation	no	yes	possibly	no	yes	no
Applications of differentiation	possibly	no	yes	possibly	yes	no
Indefinite integrals	no	yes	possibly	no	yes	no
Definite integrals	no	yes	possibly	possibly	yes	no
Applications of DI	possibly	possibly	yes	yes	yes	no

Source: authors

Fig. 1: An example of using the software Geogebra 3D in the solution control phase

Source: authors

The advantage is also the elimination of numerical errors. An example of the use of mathematical software in a second way is shown in Fig. 1. The Geogebra 3D software was used in the phase of checking the correctness of the analytical geometry task solution. The task was to analytically determine the relative position of the straight line and the planes. By displaying the given straight line and planes, the student can check the correctness of his calculation. From the visualisation through the mathematical software Geogebra 3D, it is clear that the line AC lies in the plane ABC and intersects the plane expressed by the equation $z=0$.

3 Results

Based on the results of the above analysis, it can be concluded that in terms of the selected criteria, the Geogebra 3D software achieves the highest values from the group of selected graphic software. (Fig. 2) Software control is intuitive and user-friendly. The software is reliable. We found no faults, so we gave it a five on a five-point scale. We assigned the same value to the availability of user support. In addition, Geogebra has a wide range of uses. This software is possible for technicians in almost all content parts of the introductory mathematics course (Fig. 4).

The graph in Fig. 3 shows that the Matrix calculator software achieved the highest values in the computational software group. We rated the difficulty of control with the number five since the control is very simple. It does not need to remember any syntax when working with the software. We consider the software reliable; we have not found any inconsistencies or inaccuracies in the calculations. Therefore, we also assigned the highest value in the calculation reliability criterion. User support is not freely available, but it is not necessary when applying the software in teaching. We assigned a value of four. However, the disadvantage of Matrix calculator software is its narrowly specialised use in the minimum number of content parts of mathematics for technicians, as can be seen from the graph in Fig. 4. Effectively, this software can only be used in the content section Matrices, systems of linear equations, determinants and vectors in E3.

Fig. 2: Comparison of graphic software

Source: authors

Fig. 3: Comparison of computational software

Source: authors

The designation of possible use in linear shapes in the E3 content area is debatable. In this content part, the software can only calculate determinants. This option is taken into account in the mathematics area above.

Fig. 4: Relative applicability in the content parts of the introductory mathematics course

Source: authors

The graph in Fig. 4 also shows that WolframAlpha software has the broadest applicability in mathematics content areas. It can teach all content parts of an introductory mathematics course in technical studies. Although this software in the evaluation achieved only the second highest values in all the examined criteria, it can be used effectively in teaching. In addition to the Geogebra 3D software mentioned above, the Desmos software is also helpful in the introductory mathematics course for technicians. It can be used in almost 70% of content parts of mathematics. Of the calculation software, the wxMaxima software has a relatively wide range of possible uses, but in most criteria, it reached values at the lower limit. It is used only sporadically in teaching, mainly due to low user-friendliness. It is the same with the use of Winplot software. It is being replaced by newer graphic programs such as Desmos and Geogebra.

The teaching model with the support of mathematical software was implemented in the online teaching of the subject Mathematics I at the Faculty of Materials Science and Technology in Trnava, Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava. In the previous and current academic year, 2023/2024, we used it, and we also used it in face-to-face teaching. We note students' positive attitudes towards the subject taught this way and positive results. Fig. 5 shows a graph of the relative success rate of solving the characteristic algebraic equation. Students had to solve the equation as part of a linear differential equation of the second order on the mathematics exam at the end of the 2022/2023 academic year. Out of the 101 evaluated written works, almost 80 per cent of the students solved the equation correctly. Just under 9 per cent solved the equation incorrectly. Some of the students did not solve the task. (Fig. 5) The results indicated that teaching with mathematics software can increase the effectiveness of mathematics teaching. The results of other research with similar issues also confirm this. (For example (Wijaya et al., 2021), (Juandi et al., 2021)).

Fig. 5: The relative number of students who solved the characteristic algebraic equation

Source: authors

4 Conclusion

It will be necessary to evaluate the pedagogical experiments conducted to verify the teaching model's didactic effectiveness with the support of mathematical software. However, preliminary results indicate that mathematical software has its justification in teaching an introductory mathematics course at a technical university. Mathematics at engineering-oriented universities often has the character of a sieve that serves to separate the successful from the unsuccessful applicants. Students often perceive mathematics as unnecessarily demanding or isolating due to the emphasis on self-importance. Those with mathematical talent can continue to prepare for the engineering profession; those who do not have this talent are viewed with distrust. Their abilities to design creative engineering solutions are not much considered. Teaching mathematics with the support of mathematical software has the ambition to change this situation. The described research aimed to analyse the selected mathematical software and propose a teaching model for the introductory mathematics course at a technical university with the support of suitable mathematical software. Part of the solution is a proposal to effectively use various open-source mathematical software in individual content parts of mathematics. In this way, we wanted to contribute to the development of mathematics teaching theory in the field of effective mathematics teaching methods with the support of mathematical software. The mentioned study was created as part of the project solution, the goal of which is the design, verification and implementation of innovative online teaching models of mathematics and informatics subjects with an emphasis on increasing the quality of educational results, focusing on a student who should be flexible, creative, with critical thinking, able to solve problems, constantly learning and working in a team.

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